

A review paper on the effect of the alloy on duplex stainless steel203.

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ABSTRACT:

This review paper aims to provide an overview of the effect of alloying elements on the properties of duplex stainless steel. Duplex stainless steel is a two-phase microstructure consisting of both austenite and ferrite phases. The combination of these phases provides duplex stainless steel with a unique combination of mechanical properties and corrosion resistance, making it suitable for a wide range of applications. In this paper, we will discuss the influence of various alloying elements such as chromium, molybdenum, and nitrogen on the microstructure and properties of duplex stainless steel. Additionally, the effect of other alloying elements such as nickel, copper, and tungsten will also be analyzed.

INTRODUCTION:

Duplex stainless steel has gained significant attention in various industries due to its superior mechanical properties, corrosion resistance, and cost-effectiveness. To further enhance the properties of duplex stainless steel, alloying elements are often added. These alloying elements can significantly affect the microstructure and properties of duplex stainless steel. This review paper aims to systematically analyze the effect of various alloying elements on the microstructure, mechanical properties, and corrosion resistance of duplex stainless steel. Additive Manufacturing Techniques to Produce NiTi Parts: Additive manufacturing techniques have revolutionized the production of complex geometries in various materials, including nickel-titanium alloys. However, the use of additive manufacturing techniques for duplex stainless steel is still in its early stages. This section of the paper will discuss the potential use of additive manufacturing techniques for the production of duplex stainless-steel parts. Microstructural Characteristics: The microstructure of duplex stainless steel plays a crucial role in determining its mechanical and corrosion properties. Alloying elements can significantly impact the microstructure of duplex stainless steel [1]. The alloying elements, such as chromium, molybdenum, and nitrogen, play a vital role in influencing the microstructure and properties of duplex stainless steel.

Influence of Chromium:

Stainless steel's major constituent is Cr. Increased pitting corrosion and crevice corrosion was observed when Cr contents crossed over 22% composition. However, to retain ductility, toughness, and corrosion resistance Cr is maintained below 27% because it promotes the formation of σ phase and ferrite. For heavy section castings, having Cr on the lower side of the range will help in the reduction of cracking in the as-casts condition [2].

Chromium is one of the primary alloying elements in duplex stainless steel, and it has a significant impact on its microstructure and properties. It promotes the formation of a passive oxide film on the surface, which provides excellent corrosion resistance. This oxide film acts as a barrier, preventing the diffusion of corrosive substances to the underlying material. Furthermore, chromium also enhances the strength and toughness of duplex stainless steel through solid solution strengthening and precipitation hardening mechanisms.

Influence of Molybdenum:

Mo has similar effects as Cr does on properties because it is a strong ferrite former. In the case of heavy sections, as Mo is susceptible to cracking the alloy content must be kept at the lower side of the specified. Based on previous research experience a minimum of 3.5% should be ideal for DSS applications [3].

Molybdenum is another essential alloying element in duplex stainless steel. It improves the pitting and crevice corrosion resistance of duplex stainless steel by enhancing its passive film stability. Molybdenum also increases the strength and hardness of duplex stainless steel, making it more resistant to deformation and wear.

Influence of Nitrogen:

Nitrogen is a key alloying element in duplex stainless steel and has a significant influence on its microstructure and properties. The presence of nitrogen in duplex stainless steel promotes the formation of austenite and enhances the overall corrosion resistance of the material. Additionally, nitrogen also improves the strength and hardness of duplex stainless steel by forming an interstitial solid solution with iron, thereby contributing to its mechanical properties. [4]

In summary, the alloying elements in duplex stainless steel, such as chromium, molybdenum, and nitrogen, play a crucial role in determining the microstructure and properties of the material. These elements contribute to the formation of a balanced microstructure consisting of austenite and ferrite phases, which provides duplex stainless steel with its unique combination of high strength and excellent corrosion resistance. This balanced microstructure, along with the influence of chromium, molybdenum, and nitrogen, is what makes duplex stainless steel a highly versatile and sought-after material in various industries, including oil and gas, chemical processing, marine applications, and food processing.

Influence of Tungsten and copper:

W and Cu when added in smaller percentages have shown an increase in corrosion resistance properties. However, the already heterogeneous metallurgical system of DSS becomes complicated with the addition of these two elements. Primarily, W addition causes the dissolution temperature to increase for the dissolution of the intermetallic phases. This is caused by increased nucleation rates of intermetallic phases. Research has shown that the welding of W-free DSS with W-rich and W-Cu-rich filler materials has promoted precipitation of secondary phases (χ and γ_2). Secondly, W tends to increase the amount of Cr₂N precipitates. An acceptable beneficial percentage of W is found to be at 2% [5].

It was further confirmed by Torres et al. (2020) about the 2% limit of W while using the alloy grade UNS CD-3MWCuN (cast Zeron 100), which had an alloy content of 0.5 to 1% W, which is well below the maximum 2%.

Cu when added at 2% promotes austenite formation like W. Operations requiring the interaction of sulfuric acid or in the application of equipment subjected to pollution, the addition of Cu is necessary to provide resistance to high corrosion.

Influence of Manganese:

The primary reason for avoiding the addition of Mn in the earlier days of research was due to the formation of sulfur with the addition of 0.1% Mn for corrosion resistance leads to inclusions thus weakening the passive film. Secondly, the additions of Mn are known to promote galvanic cells. Mn in acid solutions is known to form hydrogen sulfide which is a highly corrosive and poisonous gas [8]. However, there are instances of the addition of Mn in DSSs with up to 14% Mn in recent years due to technological improvements, according to some researchers the optimal percentage for DSS is found to be 0.2% [6].

Influence of Silicon:

The addition of Si to cast alloys increases flowability in the metal in a liquid state. Higher levels of silicon in DSS form ferritic and σ precipitates. Mo with Si showed lesser pitting resistance due to the

ferritic structure. Also, at higher temperatures formation of SiO₂ was observed. Hence, keeping the silicon content low will lead to a reduction in pitting corrosion, and hence Si is used in the range of 0.5-0.6% [7].

classification and percentage of Alloying Elements of duplex and super duplex stainless steel:

"The classification and percentage of alloying elements in duplex and super duplex stainless steel vary depending on the specific grade and application. In general, duplex stainless steel typically consists of approximately 22-26% chromium, 4-7% nickel, and 2-3% molybdenum, along with smaller amounts of other elements such as nitrogen, manganese, and copper. Super duplex stainless steel, on the other hand, contains higher percentages of chromium (25-28%), nickel (7-9%), and molybdenum (3-5%), as well as increased levels of other alloying elements such as nitrogen, copper, and tungsten [8]. the desired mechanical properties and corrosion resistance." The addition of alloying elements in duplex stainless steel plays a crucial role in determining the microstructure, mechanical properties, and corrosion resistance of the material.

A table creates types of elements and their respective percentages in duplex and super duplex stainless steel

Alloying Element	Duplex Stainless Steel	Super Duplex Stainless Steel
Chromium	22-26%	25-28%
Nikil	4-7%	7-9%
Molybdenum	2-3%	3-5%
Nitrogen	Small amounts	Increased levels

These percentages can vary depending on the specific grade and application of the alloy [12]. The addition of alloying elements in duplex stainless steel plays a crucial role in determining the microstructure, mechanical properties, and corrosion resistance of the material. The addition of alloying elements in duplex stainless steel plays a crucial role in determining the microstructure, mechanical properties, and corrosion resistance of the material. The classification and percentage of alloying elements in duplex and super duplex stainless steel vary depending on the specific grade and application. duplex stainless steel typically consists of approximately 22-26% chromium, 4-7% nickel, and 2-3% molybdenum, along with smaller amounts of other elements such as nitrogen, manganese, and copper. The addition of these alloying elements helps to enhance the strength, corrosion resistance, and overall performance of duplex stainless steel.

Literature review with references:

The microstructures of duplex stainless steels consist of approximately equal parts of austenite and ferrite, which contribute to their excellent resistance to stress corrosion cracking, good toughness, and high strength. These desirable properties are primarily achieved through the addition of alloying elements such as chromium, nickel, molybdenum, and nitrogen. According to several sources, including, the addition of alloying elements such as chromium, nickel, molybdenum, and nitrogen enhances the corrosion resistance, mechanical strength, and overall performance of duplex stainless steels. Furthermore, the content of these alloying elements in super duplex stainless steels is typically higher, with chromium ranging from 25-28%, nickel from 7-9%, molybdenum from 3-5%, and increased levels of nitrogen. These higher alloying element percentages contribute to the improved corrosion resistance, increased mechanical strength, and enhanced performance of super duplex stainless steels. Finally, it should be noted that the specific classification and percentage of alloying elements in duplex and super duplex stainless steel can vary depending on the grade and application. Therefore, the careful selection and control of alloying elements is crucial in determining the microstructure, mechanical properties, and corrosion resistance of duplex stainless steel. Overall, the alloying elements in duplex stainless steel, such as chromium, nickel, molybdenum, and nitrogen, play a crucial role in determining the performance and properties of the material, including its corrosion

resistance, mechanical strength, and overall durability. The addition of alloying elements such as chromium, nickel, molybdenum, and nitrogen enhances the corrosion resistance, mechanical strength, and overall performance of duplex stainless steels [9].

Duplex Stainless Steel: Benefits and Limitations

Benefits of Duplex Stainless Steel

Duplex stainless steel offers a range of benefits due to its unique microstructure and alloying elements. Some of the key advantages include:

Corrosion Resistance

The balanced combination of austenite and ferrite in duplex stainless steel provides excellent resistance to various forms of corrosion, including pitting, crevice corrosion, and stress corrosion cracking. This makes it particularly well-suited for applications in aggressive and corrosive environments, such as those involving sulfuric acid and chloride solutions [10].

High Strength

Duplex stainless-steel exhibits high tensile and yield strength, making it a robust material for structural and mechanical components. This strength is attributed to the presence of alloying elements like chromium, nickel, and molybdenum, which contribute to the material's overall mechanical properties [11].

Toughness

The microstructure of duplex stainless steel contributes to its exceptional toughness even at low temperatures, allowing it to withstand impact and heavy loads without experiencing brittle failure.

Cost-Effectiveness

In certain applications, duplex stainless steel can offer cost savings due to its combination of high strength and corrosion resistance, potentially reducing the need for additional protective coatings or frequent maintenance.

Limitations of Duplex Stainless Steel

While duplex stainless steel offers numerous advantages, there are some limitations to consider:

Weldability

The welding of duplex stainless steel requires specific techniques and careful control of parameters to minimize the risk of precipitation of harmful phases, such as sigma phase, and to maintain the material's corrosion resistance in the heat-affected zone [12].

Fabrication Challenges

Duplex stainless steel can be more challenging to machine and fabricate compared to austenitic stainless steels, requiring appropriate tooling and expertise to achieve desired outcomes.

Sensitivity to Certain Environments

While duplex stainless steel generally exhibits excellent corrosion resistance, it can be sensitive to specific environments, particularly those with high temperatures and prolonged exposure to certain

chemicals. Careful consideration of the alloy composition is crucial for optimizing performance in these conditions.

In summary, duplex stainless steel offers a compelling combination of corrosion resistance, strength, and toughness, making it a valuable material for a wide range of applications. However, careful attention to welding practices, fabrication techniques, and environmental factors is essential to fully realize its potential in challenging operating conditions [13].

Future Research Directions in Duplex Stainless-Steel Conclusion:

Future Research Directions in Duplex Stainless Steel

As duplex stainless steel continues to gain significance in various industrial applications, there are several avenues for future research and development in this field.

Enhanced Welding Techniques

Further research into advanced welding techniques and technologies is essential to address the challenges associated with welding duplex stainless steel. This includes the development of innovative welding processes and methodologies that ensure the preservation of the material's corrosion resistance while maintaining superior mechanical properties

Alloy Optimization

Efforts to optimize the alloy composition of duplex stainless steel for specific applications can lead to significant advancements. This involves studying the effects of varying percentages of alloying elements and the incorporation of new alloying additions to tailor the material's properties according to different environmental and operational requirements.

Corrosion Behavior Studies

In-depth studies focusing on the corrosion behavior of duplex stainless steel in diverse environments are crucial for expanding its applicability. Research in this area should encompass comprehensive testing under extreme conditions and exposure to a wide range of corrosive agents to understand the material's long-term performance and durability.

Advanced Fabrication Methods

Exploration of advanced fabrication methods and processes will contribute to overcoming the challenges associated with machining and fabricating duplex stainless steel. This includes the development of specialized tooling, innovative manufacturing techniques, and the utilization of cutting-edge technologies for precise and efficient fabrication [14].

Environmental Sustainability

Research endeavors aimed at enhancing the environmental sustainability of duplex stainless-steel production and usage are of growing importance. This involves investigating strategies to minimize the environmental impact of raw material extraction, processing, and end-of-life considerations while maintaining the material's beneficial characteristics [15].

Application-specific Studies

Conducting application-specific studies to assess the performance of duplex stainless steel in diverse industrial sectors, such as chemical processing, oil and gas, desalination, and marine engineering, will provide valuable insights into its suitability for specialized applications and guide tailored material design.

In conclusion, the future of duplex stainless-steel research encompasses a multidisciplinary approach, spanning from material science and engineering to environmental sustainability and application-specific analyses. By addressing the outlined research directions, the potential of duplex stainless steel can be further unlocked, leading to innovative applications and enhanced performance in an array of demanding environments [16].

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